

Adaptation to the intracellular environment of primary human macrophages influences drug susceptibility of *Mycobacterium tuberculosis*

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Keywords

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Abstract

As a facultative intracellular pathogen, *M. tuberculosis* (Mtb) is highly adapted to evading antibacterial mechanisms in phagocytic cells. Both the macrophage and pathogen experience transcriptional and metabolic changes from the onset of phagocytosis. To account for this interaction in the assessment of intracellular drug susceptibility, we allowed a 3-day preadaptation phase post-macrophage infection prior to drug treatment. We found that intracellular Mtb in human monocyte-derived macrophages (MDM) presents dramatic alterations in susceptibility to isoniazid, sutezolid, rifampicin and rifapentine when compared to axenic culture. Infected MDM gradually accumulate lipid bodies, adopting a characteristic appearance reminiscent of foamy macrophages in granulomas. Furthermore, TB granulomas in vivo develop hypoxic cores with decreasing oxygen tension gradients across their radii. Accordingly, we evaluated the effects of hypoxia on preadapted intracellular Mtb in our MDM model. We observed that hypoxia induced greater lipid body formation and no additional shifts in drug tolerance, suggesting that the adaptation of intracellular Mtb to baseline host cell conditions under normoxia dominates changes to intracellular drug susceptibility. Using unbound plasma concentrations in patients as surrogates for free drug concentrations in lung interstitial fluid, we estimate that intramacrophage Mtb in granulomas are exposed to bacteriostatic concentrations of most study drugs.

Introduction

Tuberculosis (TB) is a devastating infectious disease caused by the bacterium *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* (Mtb). The disease affected 10 million and killed 1.45 million people in 2018 alone [1]. The COVID-19 pandemic has reversed years of progress in reducing TB disease burden. This is exemplified by an 18% decline in TB diagnoses from 2019 to 2020, and an increase to 1.3 million TB deaths among HIV-negative patients [2]. This stresses the critical need for new, safe and effective drug regimens. Treatment of uncomplicated, drug-sensitive TB is long and intensive, requiring up to four antibiotics given for at least six months. The need for prolonged multidrug treatment is in part due to the presence of phenotypically diverse subpopulations of Mtb, also known as 'persisters', that exhibit tolerance to normally bactericidal concentrations of antibiotics [3].

As part of the innate immune response, Mtb is engulfed by several phagocytic host cell types that include macrophages, neutrophils and dendritic cells [4]. Mtb-infected macrophages in particular are involved in the control of bacterial burden, modulation of granuloma formation, coordination of immune responses and TB dissemination [5]. During the early stages of TB infection, alveolar macrophages within distal airways are the most commonly infected host cell type, providing a conducive niche for the pathogen while they relocate to lung interstitium and proliferate to form aggregates, thereby initiating granuloma formation [6]. The intracellular pathogen is exposed to a range of stress responses which include reactive oxygen species (ROS) [7], nitric oxide [8, 9] and acidic phagosomal pH [10]. However, as a highly adapted facultative intracellular pathogen, Mtb is able to successfully evade the antibacterial mechanisms of phagocytic cells in addition to manipulating various aspects of the host's molecular regulatory machinery to benefit its own long term intracellular survival [4, 10, 11]. A detailed study of replication and transcription dynamics of intra-macrophage Mtb revealed that the first 3 days of infection are characterized by simultaneous rapid bacterial growth and death, along with maximal changes in up-regulated and down-regulated gene expression [12]. Specific transcriptional changes include upregulation of genes required for the utilization of fatty acids as a carbon source and genes associated with anaerobic respiratory pathways [13, 14]. Also, Mtb upregulates iron sequestration, cell wall maintenance and DNA repair pathways [14]. The infected macrophage itself experiences gradual changes in gene expression in a time-dependent manner from the onset of phagocytosis [15], revealing that the host cell presents a dynamic environment instead of a static one.

Over the years, several *in vitro* screening assay platforms have been developed for the assessment of intracellular Mtb antibiotic susceptibility. Classically, such assays commence drug treatment a few hours

after macrophage infection (**Table 1**). Hence, internalized *Mtb* is only permitted a short period of time to preadapt to the intra-macrophage environment and associated stressors prior to drug exposure. Fluorescent reporter strains are sometimes used to increase the throughput of such screening platforms [16, 17]. Due to its robustness and ease of handling, the human leukemia monocytic cell line THP-1 and Abelson leukemia virus-transformed BALB/c mouse cell line RAW 264.7 are frequently used in intracellular *Mtb* drug screening platforms (**Table 1**). Indeed, differentiated THP-1 macrophages (THPM) display similar bacterial uptake, cellular viability and cytokine secretion patterns to primary human monocyte-derived macrophages (MDM) [18, 19], making the former indispensable to high throughput screening models.

Foamy macrophages (FM) are hallmarks of TB granulomas and are frequently visualized in a distinct layer directly surrounding the caseous core in animal models of TB infection and patients [20-23]. *Mtb* infection induces lipid body (LB) accumulation in host macrophages [22, 24] while the release of *Mtb* cell wall lipids from infected macrophages into the extracellular milieu has been suggested to induce surrounding uninfected macrophages to accumulate LB as well. This contributes to FM formation, caseum accumulation and the overall growth of human TB granulomas [24]. Furthermore, poor vasculature within the core of such granulomas contributes to decreasing oxygen tension gradients across their radii. C3HeB/FeJ mice [25, 26], guinea pigs [27, 28], rabbits [28], cynomolgus macaques [28] and humans [29] develop hypoxic granulomas where the partial pressure of oxygen at their cores fall below 10 mm Hg (< 1.3 % O₂). Oxygen starvation of axenic *Mtb* cultures in vitro have been shown to induce tolerance to many TB drugs [30]. Also, macrophages cultured under hypoxia (1% O₂) accumulate triglyceride (TAG) -rich LB [31, 32], as a result of increased TAG biosynthesis, reduced β -oxidation of fatty acids and increased expression of adipocyte differentiation-related protein (ADRP) [33]. As the primary niche for intracellular *Mtb* within the host, FM are recognized as potential targets of metabolic interventions in host directed therapy. While FM play critical roles in granuloma development and maintenance, they also experience diminished phagocytic and bactericidal activities [5]. Furthermore, evidence suggests that host TAG and cholesterol esters (CE) contained in LB are important carbon sources for mycobacteria during infection [33]. The caseous core of necrotic granulomas, which is similarly abundant in TAG and CE [20], is home to an extremely drug-tolerant subpopulation of *Mtb* [34]. Hence, we were prompted to investigate how hypoxic conditions influence the drug susceptibility of intracellular *Mtb*.

In this work, we first determined the drug susceptibility of preadapted intracellular *Mtb* in human MDM. We relied on primary human MDM to reflect the immunopharmacology of infected macrophages in cellular and necrotic pulmonary granulomas of TB patients. We demonstrated that MDM gradually

accumulate lipid bodies in response to Mtb infection, and that the susceptibility of the intracellular pathogen to certain antibiotics is markedly altered. Further work explored how hypoxia influences the drug susceptibility of intracellular Mtb. In our model, hypoxia induces further LB accumulation and effectively controls intracellular Mtb growth in MDM but doesn't produce additional shifts in antibiotic tolerance.

Materials and Methods

Chemical compounds

4 mM DMSO stocks of rifampicin (GoldBio Biotechnologies, USA), isoniazid (Sigma Aldrich, USA), ethambutol (Alfa Aesar, USA), rifapentine (Acros Organics, USA), moxifloxacin (TSZ Chemicals, USA), levofloxacin (ChemImpex Intl Inc, USA), sutezolid (Pfizer, USA), linezolid (Wedgewood Pharmacies, USA), delamanid (Otsuka Pharmaceutical Company Ltd, Japan), pretomanid (BioDuro, USA), bedaquiline (ChemShuttle, USA) and SQ-109 (Sequella Inc, USA) were prepared and stored at -20°C.

Human PBMC -derived monocyte isolation and differentiation

Human peripheral blood mononuclear cells (PBMCs) were isolated from freshly packed human blood (New York Blood Center) by Ficoll separation and purified using the EasySep Human CD14 Positive Selection Kit II (Stemcell Technologies, Canada) according to the manufacturer's instructions. Blood was diluted 1:1 in phosphate-buffered saline (PBS; Gibco, USA) and 20 ml was carefully layered over 15 ml Ficoll (GE Healthcare, Sweden). After centrifugation for 30 minutes at 530 g, the mononuclear cell layer was isolated and washed four times with PBS. After centrifugation for 15 minutes at 500 g, the supernatant was removed and the cell pellet re-suspended in PBS. Following a final centrifugation step for 10 minutes at 100 g to remove platelets, the cell pellet was re-suspended in RPMI 1640 medium supplemented with 10 % human serum AB (Sigma-Aldrich, USA). The number of viable cells in the suspension was counted, diluted to a density of 10^8 cells/ml and transferred to a 14 ml round-bottom tube (Falcon, USA). Easysep Human CD14 Positive Selection Cocktail II (CD14 antibodies) was added (100 μ l per 1 ml of cell suspension) and incubated for 10 minutes at room temperature. Then, EasySep Dextran RapidSpheres (anti-CD14 magnetic beads) were added for 3 minutes. CD-14-expressing cells were isolated using an EasySep magnet for immunomagnetic positive selection, washed 3 times with EasySep buffer, eluted and re-suspended in RPMI 1640 supplemented with 10% human serum, 1 % penicillin/streptomycin (Gibco, USA) and 10 ng/ml macrophage colony -stimulating factor (M-CSF, R&D

Systems, USA). Monocytes differentiated into macrophages over 6 days with medium replacement after the fourth day.

Macrophage infection and drug treatment

In all drug susceptibility assays, 5×10^4 human monocyte-derived macrophages (MDM) were seeded per well in black, clear-bottom 96-well plates (Greiner Bio-One, Germany). Macrophages were infected with a *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* (*Mtb*) Erdman strain that constitutively expresses the mCherry far-red fluorescent protein under the *smyc* promoter (a kind donation from David Russell) [35]. This Erdman strain was cultured in Middlebrook 7H9 (Sigma-Aldrich, USA) broth supplemented with 0.05% Tween 80, 0.2% glycerol, 10% albumin-dextrose-catalase (ADC) and 25 $\mu\text{g}/\text{ml}$ kanamycin. Cultures were grown to an optical density (OD_{600}) of 0.6 to 0.8. The culture was centrifuged and re-suspended in supplemented RPMI 1640 medium to the density of 10^8 bacteria per ml. This culture was vortexed for 1 minute with glass beads to de-clump bacteria prior to macrophage infection. 5×10^4 bacilli were added per well to achieve a multiplicity of infection (MOI) of 1:1. After a 4 h, cells were washed 3 times with 200 μL PBS per well to remove extracellular bacilli. Finally, 200 μL supplemented FluoroBrite DMEM (Gibco, USA), was added to each well. Infected macrophage cultures were then incubated for 3 days under normoxic (5% CO_2 , 21% O_2) or hypoxic (5% CO_2 , 1% O_2) conditions as indicated. Hypoxic conditions were maintained in a BioSpherix incubator subchamber (C-Chamber, BioSpherix, USA).

On the day of treatment initiation, FluoroBrite DMEM medium in each well was refreshed. Each drug was spiked into cell culture wells such that they were tested at 8 different concentrations from 0.001 to 20 μM . The final DMSO content in each well was 0.5%. These cultures were incubated for 5 days at 5% CO_2 and the appropriate oxygen tension with medium and drug replacements on Day 3. mCherry fluorescence signals (572 / 610 nm, ex/em) were measured at the end of the experiment using a Tecan Infinite 200 Pro plate reader. Exact bacterial burdens were determined by colony forming unit (CFU) enumeration. The cell culture medium was removed from each well and cells were lysed with 200 μL 0.5 % Triton X-100. Lysates were plated onto complete Middlebrook 7H11 agar (Sigma Aldrich, USA). Based on CFU data, MIC_{90} was defined as the drug concentration that inhibits intracellular *Mtb* growth by 90% compared to day 5 untreated controls. MBC_{90} was defined as the drug concentration that kills 90% of intracellular *Mtb* compared to the day 0 control. With regards to mCherry fluorescence data, day 5 readings from each well were corrected for respective day 0 readings. EC_{90} was defined as the effective concentration that reduces fluorescence readings by 90% compared to the day 5 untreated controls. Macrophage infections and drug

treatments were repeated with multiple blood donors. Additional growth inhibition curves are presented in **Supplementary Figure 1** to reflect donor-to-donor variability.

Replicating broth culture MIC assays

The *Mtb* Erdman reporter strain was grown in supplemented Middlebrook 7H9 medium with 25 µg/ml kanamycin to the mid-log phase. A D300e Digital Dispenser (Tecan, Switzerland) was used to spot each drug on clear 96-well flat-bottom plates. The *Mtb* cultures were diluted in 7H9 medium to a low optical density (600nm) of 0.04 and 200 µl of culture was added to each well. The DMSO content of all wells was normalized to 1%. Plates were sealed with breathable adhesive plate seals and incubated at 37°C for 5 days. Each well was then resuspended and absorbance was read at 600 nm with an Infinite M200 PRO microplate reader (Tecan). MIC₉₀ was defined as the drug concentration that inhibits *Mtb* growth by 90% compared to DMSO-only control wells.

Confocal microscopy

For confocal imaging, 1×10^6 PBMCs were plated in 0.4 ml medium on single-well LabTek chamber slides (Nalge Nunc International, Denmark) and infected with the mCherry Erdman *Mtb* strain at an MOI of 1:1 as described above. At regular time intervals, infected macrophages were fixed with BD Cytofix Fixation Buffer (BD Biosciences) for 30 minutes at room temperature and washed twice with PBS. Then, cells were exposed to 10 µM Bodipy 493/503 (Thermo Fisher) in PBS for 15 minutes, in the dark, to stain for cytoplasmic lipid droplets. After 3 washes with PBS, cells were incubated with 300 nM DAPI in PBS for 5 minutes at room temperature to stain macrophage nuclei. After 3 final washes with PBS, slides were mounted with Prolong[®] Gold Antifade reagent (Thermo Fisher). Stained slides were examined with a Nikon Ti2 inverted fluorescent microscope. Data analysis was conducted using NIS-Elements software version 5.11.02.

Flow cytometry

For flow cytometry, 5×10^5 macrophages / well were plated in 12-well plates (Costar, USA) and infected as described above. At regular time intervals, macrophages were washed twice with PBS and incubated with 5 mM EDTA for 30 minutes at 37 °C. Then, macrophages were gently removed from the bottom of each well and centrifuged at 500g for 5 minutes. Cell pellets were resuspended in 220 µL BD Cytofix Fixation buffer. After fixing for 1 hour, the cells were washed twice with PBS, stained with 500 µL of 2 µM Bodipy in PBS for 15 minutes in the dark and then washed thrice with PBS. Stained macrophages were stored in FACS buffer (0.5 % bovine serum albumin) at 4 °C in the dark. On the day of analysis, samples

were passed through a 35 μ M cell strainer (Thermo Scientific, USA). Samples were run on a BD FACSymphony Flow Cytometer A3 (BD Biosciences). Data was analyzed using the FlowJo software version 10.6.2 (BD Biosciences). All data was corrected for blank well readings absent of host and bacterial cells.

Viability assay

The viability of Mtb-infected MDM under normoxia and hypoxia was tracked using the LDH (lactate dehydrogenase) Cytotoxicity Assay Kit II (Abcam; Cambridge, United Kingdom) according to the manufacturer's instructions. Briefly, media was collected from MDM-containing wells at regular time intervals and treated with the WST substrate mix. After 30 minutes, absorbance was read at 450 nm with the reference wavelength of 650 nm. Percentage cytotoxicity was calculated as instructed using 'High control' wells treated with Cell Lysis Solution. Data is expressed as percentage viability.

Statistical analysis

All fluorescence and absorbance –based dose response curves were plotted with Graphpad Prism software version 9.0. Data is expressed as percent growth inhibition and curves were fit using nonlinear regression. The correlation between CFU-based and mCherry-based growth inhibition curves was assessed using the Pearson correlation coefficient and expressed as R^2 values. Statistical significance of flow cytometry data was determined using unpaired two-tailed t tests.

Results

Mtb preadaptation to the intramacrophage environment alters tolerance to some drugs

Our first objective was to determine the antibiotic susceptibility of preadapted intracellular Mtb in a manner compatible with medium-throughput screening platforms. Human PBMC-derived macrophages (MDM) were infected with the Mtb Erdman strain at an MOI of 1. Intracellular Mtb was allowed a 3-day preadaptation period within normoxic MDM prior to 5 days of drug exposure (**Figure 1A**). We selected a panel of first and second-line tuberculosis drugs, and several compounds in late stages of clinical development. Concentrations exceeding 20 μM were avoided in order to prevent drug-induced cytotoxicity of infected macrophages [36]. On the 8th day of the assay, the antitubercular activity of each compound was determined by CFU enumeration and fluorescence detection. Under normoxic conditions, we found good correlations between percent growth inhibition measured by CFU enumeration and mCherry fluorescence for all 12 drugs (**Figure 1B**); R^2 values were greater than 0.8 (**Table 2**). This observation demonstrated that the detection of fluorescent reporter Mtb strains enables the accurate and high-throughput evaluation of bacteriostatic drug activity under normoxic conditions. In this assay, isoniazid, rifapentine, sutezolid and delamanid were the most potent study drugs, with $\text{MIC}_{90\text{s}}$ below 0.1 μM . Rifampicin, moxifloxacin, pretomanid, bedaquiline and SQ109 had $\text{MIC}_{90\text{s}}$ that ranged between 0.1 and 1 μM . Ethambutol, levofloxacin and linezolid were the least efficacious against preadapted intracellular Mtb, with $\text{MIC}_{90\text{s}}$ between 1 and 5 μM . When compared to replicating Mtb broth cultures, we noted that the susceptibility of preadapted Mtb Erdman to isoniazid and sutezolid is >10-fold greater in MDM. Both rifamycins, however, are >10-fold less potent in the MDM model when compared to extracellular Mtb (**Table 2**).

Hypoxia does not increase intracellular drug tolerance

In necrotic lesions, a substantial population of infected macrophages resides in deep cellular layers in the direct vicinity of the necrotic core, where reduced oxygen tension is found [37] due to impaired vascular efficiency [38]. To determine how hypoxia influences the drug tolerance of preadapted intracellular Mtb, MDM were infected as described above and incubated under hypoxia (under 1 % O_2 , 5 % CO_2) for the course of the experiment [32]. Drug treatment commenced 3 days after infection and lasted for 5 days (**Figure 1A**). By studying the growth kinetics of intracellular Mtb using CFU enumeration and fluorescence detection of mCherry, we observed poor intracellular bacterial growth at 1% O_2 (**Figure 2A**). In addition, the appearance of spherical LB were observed in infected macrophages under a microscope in the

brightfield mode (**Supplementary Figure 2**). Both normoxic and hypoxic infected cells were stained with Bodipy 493/503, a lipophilic fluorescent probe that stains intracellular neutral lipids [39]. Using confocal microscopy, we observed that Mtb infection induces gradual LB accumulation in MDM (**Figure 2B**). Analyzing infected MDM from day 8 by flow cytometry, we found a small but significant increase in Bodipy staining under hypoxia ($p = 0.04$) (**Figure 2C**). Altogether, these results indicate that Mtb-infected human macrophages accumulate LB while hypoxia induces further intracellular lipid accumulation. We determined the drug susceptibility of preadapted intracellular Mtb in hypoxic MDM using the model illustrated in **Figure 1A**. Infected macrophages were treated with the same 12 antitubercular drugs and compounds for 5 days. Due to poor intracellular Mtb growth within hypoxic MDM, we recorded bactericidal activity (MBC_{90}) rather than inhibitory activity (MIC_{90}) as a measure of drug potency. We found that all but 2 drugs had the same MBC_{90} against intracellular Mtb under hypoxia (**Table 3**). Hence, we demonstrated that hypoxia does not significantly alter the drug susceptibility phenotype of preadapted intracellular Mtb.

Major TB drugs achieve bacteriostatic concentrations in cellular granuloma compartments

To determine whether key first and second line TB drugs achieve adequate concentrations at relevant sites of infection, we compared the intracellular MIC_{90} and MBC_{90} of our panel of drugs in the human MDM model to the unbound plasma concentrations achieved in TB patients receiving standard doses at steady-state (**Supplementary Table 1**). Unbound plasma concentrations were used as surrogates for free drug concentrations in the interstitial fluid of lung tissue and associated cellular granulomas, according to the prevailing concept that free drug equilibrates passively between plasma and extracellular tissue compartments [40, 41]. We found that the MIC_{90s} of isoniazid, ethambutol, rifampicin, rifapentine, linezolid, sutezolid and pretomanid are within achievable peak-to-trough unbound plasma concentration ranges (**Figure 3**). Unbound plasma concentrations of moxifloxacin and levofloxacin exceed their MIC_{90s} throughout the dosing interval. Delamanid, bedaquiline and SQ109 did not display 90% growth inhibition or cidal activity within achievable peak-to-trough unbound plasma concentration ranges.

Discussion

The histopathologic analyses of lesions from resected patient lungs revealed that Mtb is most numerous at the luminal surface of cavities where they reside predominantly within macrophages [23]. As a facultative intracellular pathogen, Mtb has developed an array of immune evasion mechanisms that enables it to persist within macrophages [11]. Mtb changes its gene expression profile during macrophage

occupation in response to various environmental stressors [14]. Such transcriptional adaptations are evident within the first few days of infection [12]. Hence, we hypothesized that preadaptation of Mtb to the intramacrophage environment would permit metabolic and physiological adaptations, producing changes to drug susceptibility. When compared to axenic replicating Mtb cultures, we found that preadapted intracellular Mtb in MDM is considerably more susceptible to isoniazid and sutezolid whereas the potencies of rifampicin and rifapentine decrease by over 10-fold. In the interest of determining how the standard THPM model with same-day drug treatment responds to these 12 anti-TB drugs, we treated Mtb Erdman -infected THPM 4 h –post infection for 5 days (**Supplementary Figure 3**). Intracellular MIC₉₀s were similarly compared to those of axenic replicating cultures. We observed that isoniazid is similarly much more potent in THPM, along with ethambutol, levofloxacin and SQ109. Furthermore, both rifamycins were similarly >5-fold less potent in infected THPM (**Supplementary Table 2**). Although direct comparisons between our MDM model and the standard THPM model were avoided due to multiple confounding factors (differences in host cell types and duration of preadaptation phase), we acknowledge that both in vitro assays produce different drug susceptibility measurements.

The interpretation of MIC₉₀ data is usually confounded by differences in inoculum size, culture media and treatment duration. In this study, drug potency was assayed over a 5-day period which is comparable with most extracellular replicating and nonreplicating Mtb screening platforms. In order to maintain macrophage viability over the entire course of the experiment, medium and drug were replaced on Day 3, resulting in two total doses of each drug. We provide additional proof that fluorescent reporter strains of Mtb can be exploited to study drug susceptibility of intracellular bacteria in a high throughput manner. We found good correlations between mCherry fluorescence and CFU burden in all drug susceptibility assays conducted in normoxia, confirming that such reporter strains are well-suited to intracellular high throughput screening assays [16, 17, 35]. Human MDM were selected over immortalized cell lines because of their greater relevance to TB immunopathology in patients although donor-to-donor variations in macrophage response is expected to influence inter-assay variability.

FM are a common feature of TB granulomas. These lipid-rich reservoirs enable the long-term persistence of Mtb within the host [22, 32]. Reduced vascular efficiency in these granulomas results in reduced oxygen tension [26, 28], which also supports the accumulation of LB in macrophages [31, 32]. Hence, in this study we investigated how hypoxia influences the drug susceptibility of preadapted intracellular Mtb in primary human macrophages. The BioSpherix incubator subchamber used in this study permits quick equilibration of 1% O₂ conditions. While medium changes and the addition of antibiotics granted short periods of re-

aeration during the course of the assay, the subchamber returns hypoxic conditions within minutes of sealing. We found that infected MDM gradually accumulate LBs even under normoxic conditions. This is in agreement with previous reports of intracellular LB accumulation in the presence of both intact Mtb and oxygenated mycolic acids from the mycobacterial cell wall [22, 42-44]. We confirmed both qualitatively and quantitatively that hypoxia (1 % O₂) induces further accumulation of cytosolic LB in Mtb infected MDM, in agreement with published data [28]. Our observation of restricted intracellular Mtb replication within foamy MDM also agrees with previous findings in hypoxia, fatty acid and mycolic acid-induced THPM and MDM [22, 32, 45]. When we assessed intracellular drug susceptibility under 1% O₂ using our MDM infection model, we found that hypoxia did not significantly alter Mtb drug susceptibility. Hypoxia-induced MDM produced little or no shifts in MBC₉₀ of the 12 drugs tested in this study despite the inclusion of a 3-day preadaptation phase which would have permitted phenotypic changes in Mtb in response to greater lipid abundance in its microenvironment. One possible explanation is that intracellular Mtb under normoxia already presents drug tolerance associated with a lipid-rich host environment. The drug tolerant phenotype we observed in preadapted intracellular Mtb under normoxic conditions likely reflects phenotypic changes associated with host LB accumulation which are not enhanced under hypoxic conditions. However, conclusive proof of this phenomenon requires comparison to a macrophage infection model in which LB accumulation is chemically or genetically hampered.

Comparing concentrations achieved at the site of intracellular infection with concentrations required to inhibit growth and kill intramacrophage bacilli in vitro, we show that adequate exposures are likely achieved for many anti-TB agents where foamy infected macrophages reside in lesions. The theoretical failure of bedaquiline, delamanid and SQ109 to achieve adequate concentrations in lung interstitial fluid is attributable to very high plasma protein binding of delamanid and bedaquiline (99.5% and >99.9, respectively) [46, 47], and relatively low overall plasma exposure and extensive tissue distribution of SQ109 [48, 49]. The concept of passive equilibration of free concentrations between plasma and tissues may not apply to these markedly hydrophobic drugs due to active uptake in host cells and/or sequestration in subcellular organelles. For example, bedaquiline accumulates in the lipid bodies of foamy macrophages and in neutrophils where it forms a reservoir subject to further redistribution into nearby microcompartments [50, 51]. Using THP-1 derived macrophages, we have measured intracellular-extracellular concentration ratios of 100-1000 for SQ109 [48], bedaquiline and delamanid (unpublished results). While bedaquiline is a proven effective drug against TB, its free plasma concentrations are not above the MIC in a typical patient. Therefore, caution should be used when applying plasma and site-of-

disease PK-PD concepts to highly hydrophobic drugs due to non-conventional complex intercompartmental clearance mechanisms at the cellular and subcellular levels.

The association between Mtb-induced LB accumulation within macrophages and changes in drug susceptibility could be related to the accumulation of intracellular lipophilic inclusions (ILIs). Mtb-containing phagosomes within FMs migrate to LBs and fuse, permitting the pathogen to synthesize host-derived TAGs and build lipid-storage vesicles of its own [22]. The induction of TAG biosynthesis redirects cellular carbon fluxes away from the tricarboxylic acid cycle (TCA), which in turn reduces mycobacterial growth [52]. Importantly, ILI accumulation in both intracellular and extracellular mycobacteria is associated with the nonreplicating persistent phenotype [22, 32, 53, 54]. Previous studies have demonstrated the accumulation of ILI in intracellular mycobacteria in normoxic in vitro models [22, 54-56]. In addition, Mtb persisters isolated from clinical sputum specimens are rich in ILI, further demonstrating that this phenotype can be acquired under normoxic conditions [53, 57]. Infected macrophages exert several immune-mediated stresses that, although being generally antimicrobial in nature, induce drug tolerance rather than synergize with antibiotic treatment [58]. Many of these pressures are generated or augmented during macrophage activation. Nitrosative stress in particular is the most potent inducer of intracellular drug tolerance [58]. Regardless of the mechanisms of drug tolerance acquisition, our study demonstrates that the macrophage environment has an impact on the intracellular activities of some drugs, making an argument for the incorporation of the host environment into drug screening strategies.

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Declarations of interest

None to declare.

Table 1. Summary of published methods for the determination of drug susceptibility against intracellular *M. tuberculosis*.

Reference	Mtb strain	Macrophage type	MOI	No. of days before treatment	No. of days of drug treatment
Cell lines					
Hartkoorn <i>et al.</i> [59]	H37Rv	THP-1	10	0	7
Agarwal <i>et al.</i> [45]	H37Rv	THP-1	5	0	6
Daniel <i>et al.</i> [32]	H37Rv	THP-1	0.1	0, 3 or 5	2
Aljayoussi <i>et al.</i> [60]	H37Rv-GFP	THP-1	0.2	1	5
Clemens <i>et al.</i> [61]	Erdman	THP-1	10	0	3
Sorrentino <i>et al.</i> [17]	Erdman-GFP	THP-1	1	0	4
Rey-Jurado <i>et al.</i> [62]	12 clinical isolates	THP-1	1	3	4
Schaaf <i>et al.</i> [63]	mc ² 6206 ^A	THP-1	25	10-14	5
Manning <i>et al.</i> [64]	H37Rv	RAW 264.7	1	1	3
Christophe <i>et al.</i> [16]	H37Rv-GFP	RAW 264.7	1	0	5
Lakshminarayana <i>et al.</i> [36]	H37Rv-GFP	RAW 264.7	1	0	5
Horváti <i>et al.</i> [65]	H37Rv	MonoMac-6	10	1	3
Liu <i>et al.</i> [58]	CDC1551	J774A.1	4	0	2-4

Primary cells					
Chanwong <i>et al.</i> [66]	H37Rv	guinea pig	10	0	3-10
Daniel <i>et al.</i> [32]	H37Rv	Human MDM	0.1	0, 3 or 5	2
Liu <i>et al.</i> [58]	CDC1551	Mouse BMDM	4	0	2-4

MOI, multiplicity of infection; GFP, green fluorescent protein; MDM, monocyte-derived macrophages from peripheral blood mononuclear cell (PBMCs); BMDM, primary bone marrow-derived macrophages; ^Δ, avirulent strain that neither replicates nor is killed during infection.

Table 2. Drug susceptibility of the Mtb Erdman reporter strain in replicating broth culture and when preadapted to the intracellular environment of human MDM under normoxia.

Drug	Replicating broth culture	Preadapted intracellular Mtb		
	MIC ₉₀ (μM)	MIC ₉₀ (μM)	EC ₉₀ (μM)	R ²
Isoniazid	3.8	0.07	0.08	0.99
Ethambutol	5.3	1.2	2.8	0.86
Rifampicin	0.005	0.3	0.3	0.98
Rifapentine	0.003	0.05	0.03	0.84
Moxifloxacin	0.16	0.4	0.3	0.99
Levofloxacin	0.67	1.2	2.8	0.85
Linezolid	1.3	4.9	1.4	0.94
Sutezolid	0.75	0.04	0.09	0.80
Pretomanid	0.45	0.4	0.4	0.92
Delamanid	0.03	0.02	0.02	0.98
Bedaquiline	0.09	0.3	0.3	1.0
SQ109	2.3	1.0	1.7	0.99

MIC₉₀ is defined as the minimum drug concentration required to inhibit bacterial replication by 90%; EC₉₀ is the MIC₉₀ equivalent as determined by mCherry fluorescence detection; R² values demonstrate the correlation between MIC₉₀ and EC₉₀ curves.

Table 3. Bactericidal activity of antituberculosis drugs against preadapted intracellular Mtb in MDM under normoxia and hypoxia.

Drug	MBC ₉₀	
	21% O ₂	1% O ₂
Isoniazid	1.25	1.25
Ethambutol	>20	20
Rifampicin	1.25	5
Rifapentine	1.25	0.31
Moxifloxacin	1.25	1.25
Levofloxacin	5	5
Linezolid	>20	>20
Sutezolid	>20	20
Pretomanid	>20	>20
Delamanid	20	20
Bedaquiline	1.25	1.25
SQ109	20	20

MBC₉₀ is defined as the minimum drug concentration required to kill 90% of intracellular bacteria, as determined by CFU enumeration.

Figure legends

Figure 1. Drug susceptibility of preadapted intracellular *M. tuberculosis* in MDM. (A) Illustration of experimental design. Human MDM were infected with a mCherry –expressing Mtb Erdman strain and incubated under normoxia (21% O₂) or hypoxia (1% O₂). Drug treatment was initiated 3 days after macrophage infection. (B) Percentage growth inhibition was measured by CFU enumeration (dark hollow circles) and mCherry fluorescence detection (light filled circles). Nonlinear regression curves were fit for each dataset and standard deviations are represent 3 technical repeats. Horizontal dotted lines indicate 50% and 90% growth inhibition. Each drug assay was performed up to three times and representative data is shown.

Figure 2. Hypoxia-induced MDM. (A) Intracellular Mtb Erdman growth kinetics under normoxia (filled circles) and hypoxia (hollow circles) measured by CFU plating (black) and mCherry fluorescence detection (red). (B) Fluorescence microscopy images of infected MDM over the 8 –day infection period. Blue, DAPI; Green, Bodipy –stained lipid bodies; Red, mCherry Mtb reporter strain. Scale bar = 5µm. (C) Infected MDM under normoxia and hypoxia were collected 8 days post-infection. Samples analyzed by flow cytometry after staining with Bodipy. Data is presented as the normalized mean fluorescence intensity (MFI) for Bodipy (green) and mCherry (red). *, p < 0.05. Experiments were performed twice and representative data is shown. (D) Percentage viability of infected MDM under normoxia and hypoxia over 8 days.

Figure 3. Dose response of intracellular *M. tuberculosis* under normoxic conditions. Bacterial burden is expressed as the mean number of CFU per well on a log scale. Green and pink boxes represent the ranges of maximum and minimum free (unbound) drug concentrations (fC_{max}), respectively, in patients receiving standard doses at steady-state (see Supplementary Table 1). Dotted lines represent MIC₉₀ of intracellular Mtb relative to Day 5 DMSO-controls. Dashed lines represent MBC₉₀ of intracellular Mtb, where applicable, relative to starting burdens on Day 0.

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